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TRANSFORM

e-book

TRANSFORM

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Table of contents

0. Introduction	p. 4
1. TRANSFORM Regions in Action	
1.1. Lombardy	p. 8
1.2. Catalonia	p. 12
1.3. Brussels-Capital Cluster	p. 16
2. Shared Learning	
2.1. Mutual Learning and Capacity Building	p. 20
2.2. CC-PES	p. 24
3. Monitoring and Evaluation	p. 27
4. People	
4.1. Partners	p. 31
4.2. Advisory Board	p. 32
5. Credits	p. 33

TRANSFORM

0. Introduction

0. Introduction

Making territorial R&I governance more open and inclusive by engaging citizens and multiple stakeholders in the definition and implementation of regional policymaking. This is the purpose of TRANSFORM - Territories as Responsive and Accountable Networks of S3 Through New Forms of Open and Responsible Decision-Making - a Coordination and Support Action funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 Programme.

To achieve its goal, TRANSFORM brought together three European regions, Lombardy (Italy), Catalonia (Spain), and Brussels-Capital (Belgium), to design and test three sound methodologies: participatory research agenda setting, citizen science, and multi-stakeholder engagement practices.

TRANSFORM builds on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), a concept promoted by the European Commission to better align research and innovation with societal views, needs, and expectations. It provides regional public authorities and other interested R&I actors with inspiring examples and practical suggestions, emerging from real regional settings and experimentations, on how to put these principles into practice.

The three regions involved in TRANSFORM implemented a mutual learning process, also pairing with CC-PES initiative in Boston (Massachusetts, US), a project aimed at opening the public dialogue on science and innovation.

At the end of its 3-year journey, TRANSFORM collected the most relevant reports, articles, and multimedia products in this e-book as an as easy-to-use guide for all interested actors.

TRANSFORM website comprises official documents and multimedia material developed during the course of the project.

[VISIT THE WEBSITE](#)

All the videos produced during the 36 months of the project can be found in the official TRANSFORM YouTube channel.

[WATCH THE VIDEOS](#)

The policy brief includes lessons learnt by the three regional clusters in the first 15 months of the project. It provides recommendations for policymakers willing to engage in experiences of local RRI grounding through citizen engagement.

[READ THE BRIEF](#)

1 .TRANSFORM Regions in Action

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LOMBARDY

1.1 Lombardy

1.1 Lombardy

In Lombardy, three partners ([Bassetti Foundation](#), cluster leader, [Lombardy Region](#) and [Finlombarda](#)) worked together to implement a participatory research agenda-setting exercise to engage citizens in defining regional R&I priorities. The process was structured mainly using deliberative methods.

In Spring 2021, around 1020 people living in Lombardy were engaged, combining a survey administered to a representative sample of the Lombardy population (targeting personal and territorial needs) and a deliberative workshop on just energy transition for all in Lombardy.

Outcomes supported Lombardy Region in identifying territorial and citizens' needs that are at the basis of the regional [Three Years Strategic Program on Research, Innovation and Technological Transfer \(2021-2023\)](#).

In June 2022, a face-to-face Citizens' Jury engaged 24 Lombardy citizens - selected according to specific socio-demographics criteria - to learn, discuss, and deliberate about regional Responsible Smart Mobility, a key theme of [Lombardy Smart Specialization Strategy \(S3\)](#). Jurors' delivered recommendations on key responsibility issues - like privacy, profiling, and inclusion - that are connected to the development of smart data-driven mobility services, which Lombardy Region has used to implement S3.

The actions and the outcomes of the entire process were described (in Italian) in the regional platform [rd](#) and presented in a public event.

This document aims at helping regional public administrations who wish to enable participatory research agenda setting actions in their local policymaking.

READ THE BRIEF

This WEBPAGE describes activities and outcomes of TRANSFORM Lombardy. It collects all the reports, videos, and multimedia material developed during the project's lifetime in Lombardy (in Italian).

VISIT THE WEBSITE

This video describes the Citizen Jury conducted in Lombardy within TRANSFORM: 24 representatives of Lombardy's population gathered for two days to learn, discuss, and deliberate about responsible smart mobility.

WATCH THE VIDEO

Citizens' Jury on Responsible Smart Mobility in Lombardy

This video describes the participatory research agenda-setting exercise conducted in Lombardy within TRANSFORM: sharing their experiences and opinions on personal and territorial needs, citizens contribute to shaping regional R&I priorities.

WATCH THE VIDEO

Citizens' and territorial needs in Lombardy

Final local event

All the activities developed and the outcomes obtained thanks to TRANSFORM in Lombardy have been presented in a local final event. Here the video of the event.

WATCH THE VIDEO

Within TRANSFORM, Giannino Bassetti Foundation edited the Italian version of the OECD report to contribute to spreading the culture and the practice of public deliberation in Italy and launched it in a public event. Here the video of the event.

VISIT THE WEBSITE

Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions. Catching the Deliberative Wave - Highlights 2020 (Italian report and launching event)

TRANSFORM
CATALONIA

1.2 Catalonia

1.2 Catalonia

The Catalan TRANSFORM cluster has developed two main activities:

- The setting up of a **Think Tank** on RRI and citizen science composed of different stakeholders from the regional R&I ecosystem, with the aim that participating organisations increase their knowledge on RRI and citizen science as well as their capacities to implement this perspective in their own strategies and projects.
- The **co-design (together with the members of the Think Tank) and implementation of 2 citizen science pilots**, with the aim of, on the one hand, transforming the local R&I policy-making cycle to more responsible approaches through citizen science.

The first pilot had the objective of contributing to the improvement of the selective waste collection system in the city of Mollet del Vallès. It consisted, first, in the co-design of a digital waste game, with the double objective of informing citizens about innovative selective collection systems (door-to-door and smart bins) and collecting their preferences and assessments regarding their possible implementation. The game was then used as a citizen science tool. 60 secondary school students from the city participated by collecting data, interpreting the results and making recommendations to the city council for a better implementation of these systems.

The second pilot aimed to contribute to the improvement of health services for endometriosis. In it, 20 women with endometriosis participated in the research, in order to deepen their experiences of the disease, the biopsychosocial variables that are affected by it and to detect needs with respect to health services. In addition, these women co-created 28 recommendations addressed to health professionals and policy makers, with the aim of improving the situation.

The roadmap provides regional public authorities and other interested R&I actors with practical suggestions, emerging from real regional settings and experimentations, on how to implement RRI principles through citizen science.

READ THE BRIEF

[News on the citizen science pilot applied to waste management](#)

VISIT THE WEBPAGE

News on the citizen science pilot applied to women's health.

VISIT THE WEBPAGE

[News on the citizen science pilot applied to women's health](#)

This policy brief summarises the findings of the citizen science pilot on endometriosis as well as first-person recommendations for improving health services for the disease and public health policies.

[READ THE BRIEF](#)

[First person recommendations to improve health care services for endometriosis](#)

[News on the Catalan Think Tank on RRI and citizen science](#)

The news item summarises the process of creating the Catalan Think Tank on RRI and citizen science, and the results of the participatory capacity building webinars carried out.

[VISIT THE WEBPAGE](#)

This executive summary describes the process and the findings of the citizen science pilot to improve the waste collection system in Mollet del Vallès.

[READ THE BRIEF](#)

[Executive summary on the results of the waste pilot](#)

TRANSFORM
BRUSSELS

1.3 Brussels - Capital region

1.3 Brussels - Capital Region

The Brussels-Capital regional cluster partners BE participation asbl and UCLouvain have implemented three pilots with the aim to involve the regional partner Innoviris in various types of multi-stakeholder engagement processes (within and outside of the academia), with a strong involvement of citizens.

The pilots clearly show the added value of such processes towards the definition of better regional R&I policies. They also show how beneficial such processes can be in terms of avoiding adverse impacts of the R&I that the region supports in the context of their regional R&I strategic programmes (such as the RIS3). The pilots will therefore inform Innoviris' future governance of R&I and they have been promoted to other Brussels-capital public agencies.

Two pilots, called AcquaSens and Algorella, have allowed innovations produced within an academic environment to address potential societal impacts through citizen engagement. It has been key for researchers and innovators of the AcquaSens and Algorella process to have the opportunity to be accompanied by RRI experts throughout the citizen engagement process. Innoviris is working on how to integrate such types of processes in the future, within R&I projects it supports.

The unsold food pilot has brought together local actors in the middle of a particularly challenging and conflicting situation, showing how multi-stakeholder engagement can be key to identifying common ground and solutions, assess impacts and provide public funders with an understanding of a complex ecosystem.

The roadmap provides regional public authorities and other interested R&I actors with practical suggestions, emerging from real regional settings and experimentations, on how to implement RRI principles through multi-stakeholder engagement.

[READ THE BRIEF](#)

[The Brussels cluster AquaSens pilot](#)

A presentation (in French) of key citizen engagement activities of one of the cluster pilots, focused on an innovation by two UCLouvain students, which aims at creating easy to use sensors to measure water quality.

[VISIT THE WEBPAGE](#)

A description (in French) of the main steps and outcomes of the pilot run by BE participation asbl, focusing on the topic of unsold food. The WEBPAGE includes links to a report (in French, Dutch and English), summarizing key outcomes of the process.

[VISIT THE WEBPAGE](#)

[The Brussels cluster unsold food pilot](#)

TRANSFORM

2. Shared learning

TRANSFORM

2.1 Mutual learning and capacity building

2.1 Mutual learning and capacity building

Shared learning is at the core of TRANSFORM activities.

The implementation of RRI at regional level must be adapted to specificities of each local context. It is for this reason that TRANSFORM clusters have developed and implemented different approaches to achieve the project core objectives. Ranging from the specific methodological approach adopted by each region to the variety of stakeholders involved and impacts achieved, the differences between clusters constitute one of the main richness of the project, and have been exploited to share and build new knowledge between consortium members. For this reason, a detailed Shared Learning Plan has been developed by WP2 leader BE participation at the beginning of the project, identifying key needs and action points together with all project partner.

The TRANSFORM shared learning process has therefore developed through three main types of activities:

Capacity building sessions involving external experts and in particular members of the project Advisory Board, who shared their expertise with the consortium.

A series of Mutual Learning Workshops, involving project partners, aimed at (in the first part of the project) building a common understanding of project aims, cluster activities implementation, and their legacy; and (in the second half of the project) sharing and learning from the methodological approach implemented by each cluster.

Cluster leaders, together with the partner in charge of the evaluation of project activities, have also been meeting monthly to keep each other informed, as well as shared challenges and views.

In this first session, Giulia Bubbolini explained the methodology of an RRI Maturity assessment of 8 European regions developed within the context of the EU-funded project MARIE (MAInstreaming Responsible Innovation in European S3). The assessment was designed and implemented to help regions assess their level of RRI maturity and identify their strengths and weaknesses in terms of RRI awareness and implementation.

WATCH THE VIDEO

In the second capacity building session, Angela Pereira contributed to showcasing an inspiring citizen engagement project called BiodiverCities, presented by Anna Paola Quaglia (JRC), which aims to enhance civil society participation in local and urban decision-making. In the second part of the session, Annelies Duerinckx presented the work of the Scivil network which promotes citizen science in Flander (Belgium).

WATCH THE VIDEO

In the third capacity building session, Louise Francis delves into citizen science and collective mapping as innovative ways to engage the community in bigger national and global issues. The session covered a broad introduction to citizen science, its main principles and typologies, as well as concrete examples of its use.

WATCH THE VIDEO

Capacity building Session 1:
the EU project MARIE, by Giulia Bubbolini

Capacity building Session 2:
Collaboration with CSOs for
citizen engagement

Capacity building Session 3:
Citizen Science

In the fourth session, Simon Burall introduced participatory innovation agenda setting, providing an extensive overview of the definitions, scopes, and methods at the basis of public deliberation for policy making. The presentation also includes a set of case studies on deliberative engagement that put citizens at the heart of decision-making.

WATCH THE VIDEO

In the last session, Anna Meroni shared her expertise in citizen engagement processes through co-design that make use of specific techniques of design activism, social innovation and sustainability, with a specific focus on food, urbanism and housing systems. In her talk she introduces and discusses two examples drawn from her experience in the field.

WATCH THE VIDEO

This Padlet provides an example of an online activity done by project members during one of the virtual Mutual Learning Workshops, where clusters were asked to reflect on “key selling points” of their citizen engagement activities that would, in their opinion, contribute to convince other regions to follow their steps.

VISIT THE WEBPAGE

Capacity building Session 4:
Participative Innovation Agenda Setting

Capacity building Session 5:
Impactful co-design processes

An example of a mutual learning activity:
clusters key selling points

TRANSFORM
BOSTON

2.2 CC-PES

2.2 Model for Co-creation and Implementation of Deliberative Forums

The National Science Foundation-funded “Building Capacity for Co-Created Public Engagement with Science” (NSF DRL-1811118) is built upon the three steps of public participation (agenda-setting, decision-making, and policy-forming) outlined in Rowe and Frewer (2005). It includes each of the CC-PES partner organization types (Informal Science Education organizations, community, civic, and scientist) in each component of the process, facilitated by an ISE organization.

The CC-PES project has enabled informal science education organizations to learn how to plan, develop, implement, and evaluate public engagement dialogue activities, or forums, that are co-created with local civic, community, and scientist partners.

CC-PES teams prototyped methods for involving the public in the entire process, including topic selection. Three different sites (Boston MA, Portland OR, and Raleigh-Durham NC) each spent 18-24 months building localized relationships, developing content, and implementing a co-created forum program.

Between January and June 2023, a 3rd round of sites, selected through a competitive application process, will continue prototyping and refining the model. With input from consultants and an external evaluation team, a CCPES Guide will be assembled and then disseminated to ISE sites at a National Summit mid-2023 (TBA).

[Thinking Outside the Blocks](#)

After 12 months of in-person relationship building, topic selection, and content generation, the Boston MA team had to suddenly switch to online activities in March 2020. They partnered with consider.it to create a seamless user experience, mimicking the program's interactive paper pieces. Data collected here, at the "decision-making" phase, contributed to the group "policy-forming" work.

[VISIT THE WEBPAGE](#)

[Wicked Hot Boston](#)

This interactive storymap depicts Urban Heat Island data requested and generated by community partners in the Greater Boston MA Area. With partners, the Museum of Science engaged a fleet of citizen scientists to collect the data, and subsequently mapped it into the user-friendly platform above.

[VISIT THE WEBPAGE](#)

TRANSFORM

3. Monitoring and Evaluation

3.1 The Challenge of Monitoring Responsibility Responsibly

TRANSFORM devoted significant resources to perform internal monitoring and evaluation, both as part of our own governance and to document and disseminate what we did, how it worked and what we learnt.

Monitoring and evaluation should also be responsible. R&I ecosystems are complex and move slowly. RRI impacts may emerge years after a project. Causal links may be difficult to establish. Moreover, if RRI is the answer, opinions differ on what the question was. We discussed this in a [blog post](#).

The challenge was much discussed among the SwafS-14 RRI projects and the Super MoRRI project, which resulted in a [discussion paper on impacts, pathways and benefits of RRI](#).

There is no scarcity of proposed RRI indicators, especially at the national level. For good reasons, most of them are never used. Indicators make sense in standardised settings. Projects such as TRANSFORM, however, succeed by understanding and inserting themselves in the regional context and knowing how to prepare and when to act at the right moments. RRI is craft and art and not industrial mass production. Hence, we opted for monitoring and evaluation approaches that accentuate reflexivity, contextuality, and double loop learning, such as [evaluative inquiry](#).

The first version of our Monitoring and Evaluation Guide is available at our [deliverable WEBPAGE](#). An updated version as well as scientific papers and a book reporting our results will be available open access at the same WEBPAGE in 2023.

This WEBPAGE on the TRANSFORM website collects all deliverables developed during the lifetime of the project. Monitoring and evaluation publications (WP7) will be available on this site in 2023.

[VISIT THE WEBPAGE](#)

[Deliverables' WEBPAGE on TRANSFORM website](#)

This WEBPAGE on the TRANSFORM website describes the contribution of TRANSFORM consortium partners from the University of Bergen to a talk presented at the REvaluation Conference in May 2022.

[VISIT THE WEBPAGE](#)

[TRANSFORM at the REvaluation Conference 2022](#)

This WEBPAGE on the TRANSFORM website briefly lists the preliminary findings of the monitoring and evaluation activities after the project's second year.

[VISIT THE WEBPAGE](#)

[RRI ASSESSMENT after the 2nd year of TRANSFORM](#)

4. People

4.1 Partners

Catalonia cluster leader

Fondazione Giannino Bassetti
per la Responsabilità nell'Innovazione

TRANSFORM Coordinator and
Lombardy cluster leader

BE
participation
Plateforme belge pour la participation citoyenne asbl

Brussels-Capital cluster leader

Generalitat
de Catalunya

Regione
Lombardia

UNIVERSITAT DE
BARCELONA

Museum of Science

UNIVERSITY OF BERGEN
Centre for the Study of the Sciences and the Humanities

4.2 Advisory Board

The TRANSFORM Advisory Board (AB) is a group of five acclaimed experts who regularly interacted with the TRANSFORM consortium throughout the project. They provided strategic guidance on different methodological approaches implemented within clusters and supported the implementation of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approaches within the Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation (S3) for each regional cluster.

Louise Francis
Citizen science for territorial innovation advisor

Simon Burrell
Participatory research agenda setting advisor

Anna Meroni
Design thinking for social media innovation

Ângela Guimarães Pereira
Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) Advisor

Giulia Bubbolini
S3 Advisor

5. Credits

E-book concept and coordination

Anna Pellizzone and Angela Simone
(*Giannino Bassetti Foundation*)

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Giannino Bassetti Foundation - BEparticipation - Science for Change -
University of Bergen - Museum of Science, Boston

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Giannino Bassetti Foundation and formicablu srl

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